

**METHODS OF TRANSMITTING SPEECH ACTS IN SIMULTANEOUS
TRANSLATION**

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Annotation

This article discusses methods of transmitting speech acts in simultaneous translation. The article consists of an annotation, keywords, introduction, main part, conclusion and a list of references, as required.

Keywords: simultaneous translation, neural speech-to-speech translation, incremental speech recognition, incremental machine translation, incremental speech synthesis

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются способы передачи речевых актов при синхронном переводе. Статья состоит из аннотации, ключевых слов, введения, основной части, заключения и списка литературы по мере необходимости.

Ключевые слова: синхронный перевод, нейронный перевод речи в речь, инкрементное распознавание речи, инкрементный машинный перевод, инкрементальный синтез речи.

The largest motivation of simultaneous speech translation is to convey spoken information in a different language with small latency. For example, in a lecture talk, a speaker often talks successively without any apparent pauses and sentence boundaries. In such cases, a pause-based or sentence-based processing suffers from large latency until a pause or sentence boundary is observed. The latency may become much larger in the latter part of a long talk due to accumulated processing delays. Incremental processing helps catch up with the original speech. Human simultaneous interpretation is demanded for the same reason. Difficulty in simultaneous speech-to-speech translation is similar to that in simultaneous human interpretation. In some language pairs with a distant word order such as English and

Japanese, human simultaneous interpretation is very challenging due to a large cognitive load to maintain long phrases in short-term memory in the interpreter's brain.

Simultaneous interpreting, the act of orally interpreting audio with only few seconds of lag time, is one of the toughest skills to master for any student of interpretation/translation. An interpreter must have the ability to listen, comprehend, and reiterate the previously stated in another language- all in a matter of seconds- while concentrating on the next statement as well. It requires a lot of decision-making, attentiveness, and knowledge. Fortunately, there are an abundance of methods to aid one in championing this skill.

One route accepted by many is to simply take a class. Within a quality class, various drills and exercises will benefit one who is learning how to interpret simultaneously. However, one does not have to necessarily take a class to develop these skills. An easy method is to listen to a famous speech and record yourself as you interpret it. After doing so, find the script for the speech and read it as you listen to your recording so that you can check yourself for accuracy. The same steps can be taken with a recorded movie, television show, or newscast by turning on the subtitles during the reviewing process. Another great way to enhance your interpretation skills is to find a mentor, a professional interpreter who has been doing the job for years. Shadowing them and gaining advice, tips, and recognition of their approach can be incredibly beneficial to you. A specific drill to help one with one's ability to predict the outcome of the message stems from *Fundamentals of Court Interpretation: Theory, Policy, and Practice*. The authors suggest taking a written passage and picking out random sentences, covering up the latter half of the sentences, and trying to predict what the covered portions will say based on the previous wording and contextual clues.

The strategy of probabilistic forecasting in case of simultaneous translation is the attempt of the translator to foresee and work out lexical, grammatical, phonetic components of the speech of the speaker before they are pronounced, basing on already received and processed (i.e. translated) information. One of the methods of

probabilistic forecasting is determination of any parts of speech in the text of the speaker. This method is especially productive when the main and semantic information of the statement is focused at the end of the sentence (Korostenski, 2017). For the first time the term "probabilistic forecasting" has been used by Russian scientist, the famous psychophysicist. According to Chernov's definition "probabilistic forecasting" is "A situation is a signal for preparation of body to react adequately to B situation. The wider range of the events which were equally often following A in the past (i.e. more uncertain is the forecast), the broader range of physiological systems will be mobilized in response to A signal. This prospective adaptation to actions in the forthcoming situation

Simultaneous translation (also known as real-time or streaming translation) is the task of generating translations incrementally given partial input only. Simultaneous translation enables interesting applications such as automatic simultaneous interpretation or international conference translations. Simultaneous systems are typically evaluated with respect to quality and latency. This year, we will have 2 tracks and 3 language pairs:

- Text-to-Text: translating the output of a streaming ASR system in real-time from English to German, English to Japanese, and English to Mandarin Chinese.
- Speech-to-Text: translating speech into text in real-time from English to German, English to Japanese, and English to Mandarin Chinese.

We want to highlight the differences with respect to last edition:

- for the text-to-text track, we will use the output of a streaming ASR system as input instead of the gold transcript. As a result, both text-to-text and speech-to-text systems will be ranked together for a given language pair.
 - we are adding Mandarin Chinese as a target language.
 - we are adding an experimental **manual evaluation** for English-to-German real-time translation
 - we are adding **human interpretation benchmark** for English-to-German speech translation

- in order to reduce the number of conditions, we use only segmented input; the manual evaluation will run on reconstructed full documents

It can be concluded that like any creative process, translation is associated with certain difficulties, one of which is translation transformations. It is safe to say that translation transformations are an important and integral aspect of translation, and they are widely used and help to overcome various difficulties. This field has been widely covered by leading linguists and translation theorists. According to the combined model of translation transformations of I. S. Alekseeva and L. S. Barkhudarov, the main types of lexical transformations used in the translation process include the following translation techniques: elementary transformations (permutations, substitutions, additions and omissions) and complex transformations (antonymic translation, descriptive translation and compensation). Translation is divided into consecutive and simultaneous translation. During a speech, the translator in the first case first listens to the speaker, writing down some part of it, and then translates, relying on his notes and memory.

Simultaneous translation is carried out simultaneously with the speaker's speech without the ability to record anything, as well as to convey the meaning and features of the speech in a short time. It is important for a simultaneous translator to have the appropriate skills of the art of translation. A special role in this translation is played by the personal qualities and skills of the simultaneous translator: clear diction, psychological stability, the ability to make quick decisions, quick reaction, and broad knowledge in various fields of science and social life, as well as cross-cultural knowledge.

Reference:

1. Алексеева И.С. Введение в переводоведение. - М.: Академия, 2004. - 352с.
2. Бархударов Л.С. Язык и перевод: Вопросы общей и частной теории перевода. Изд. 3-е - М.: Издательство ЛКИ, 2010. - 240 с.

3. Комиссаров В.Н. Современное переводоведение. Учебное пособие. – М.: ЭТС, 2002. – 326 с.

4. Чернов Г.В. Основы синхронного перевода. Учебник для институтов и факультетов ин.яз. -М., Высш.шк., 1987. -257 с.

5. Тошматов, О., Миргиязова, М., & Ёкубов, У. (2020). ВАЖНОСТЬ ОБУЧЕНИЯ СПЕЦИАЛИЗИРОВАННОГО АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ЧЕРЕЗ ЧТЕНИЕ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВЮРИСТОВ. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (V).

6. Mustafakulovich, R. M., Shokirovich, T. O., & Ishnazarovna, M. N. (2020). SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING AS A SPECIAL INTERPRETER ACTIVITY. PROS AND CONS OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (V).